

Traffic-aware ONU Grouping and Downstream Bandwidth Allocation for Multicast Services in Flexible-Rate PONs

XIANG LU,^{1,2} XINSHUI WEI,¹ ZHIYUAN ZHONG,¹ JUN LI,^{1,*} AND LUIS VELASCO²

¹ School of Electronic and Information, Soochow University, Suzhou 215031, China

²Advanced Broadband Communications Center (CCABA), Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), 08034 Barcelona, Spain

*Corresponding author: ljun@suda.edu.cn

In flexible-rate passive optical networks (PON), optical network units (ONU) with different channel conditions can achieve different data rates by implementing flexible transmission parameters, e.g., modulation format, thereby enhancing system capacity. Correspondingly, the downstream frame is divided into multiple subframes, each being received and processed only by ONUs in its targeted group. However, for downstream multicast services, the data needs to be duplicated and encapsulated into multiple subframes for ONUs belonging to different groups, resulting in data redundancy and degradation of effective throughput (i.e., throughput without redundant data). To improve resource utilization, ONU grouping should be dynamically adjusted according to both channel conditions and time-varying network factors, e.g., traffic loads and multicast memberships. For this, we first enhance the current downstream scheduling protocol to support dynamic ONU grouping in a multicast scenario and propose a traffic-aware ONU grouping (TAOG) algorithm to improve effective throughput, which optimizes ONU grouping by considering the time-varying network conditions. As ONUs belonging to different groups have different data rates, we further propose a group-based downstream time slot allocation (GBDTA) algorithm to adjust time slots for each service by considering their demands and ONU data rates. Exhaustive simulation results show that the integrated TAOG-GBDTA scheme adapts effectively to dynamic network conditions and, compared to conventional schemes, it effectively improves effective throughput, reduces redundancy, and achieves lower packet latency under various multicast scenarios.

1. INTRODUCTION

Time division multiplexing-passive optical networks (TDM-PON), operating on a point-to-multipoint (P2MP) architecture, are among the most commonly-used access network technologies. Notably, International Telecommunication Union-Telecommunication Standardization Sector (ITU-T) PONs, e.g., Gigabit PON (GPON) and XG(S)-PON, are widely deployed, especially in the scenario of fiber to the home (FTTH) [1]. To meet the stringent quality of service (QoS) requirements of emerging new broadband services, ITU-T has standardized the next-generation higher speed TDM-PON [2-7]. In a typical ITU-T TDM-PON, a single optical line terminal (OLT) is connected to multiple optical network units (ONU) via an optical distribution network (ODN). In the upstream direction, each ONU transmits its data to the OLT in a burst mode within allocated time slots. In the downstream direction, the OLT aggregates data for all ONUs into a frame with a fixed length of 125 μ s, referred to as the downstream PHY frame, and broadcasts it continuously to all ONUs. Each ONU identifies and retrieves its data from the downstream PHY frame. Furthermore, both upstream and downstream transmissions operate at a uniform, constant peak data rate across all ONUs [8,9]. In this regard, these TDM-PONs are categorized as fixed-rate PONs.

However, the channel conditions between ONUs and the OLT can vary significantly due to optical path loss (OPL) influenced by factors such as the physical distance and the number of splitters [10-13]. In a fixed-rate PON, the constant peak data rate is constrained by the worst-case optical budget, rather than considering the actual channel conditions experienced by each ONU [10,13]. As a result, ONUs with better channel conditions operate below their potential capacity, thereby limiting the overall system capacity. To address this issue, a promising approach is to differentiate the peak data rates of ONUs by allowing ONUs with better channel conditions to operate at higher data rates while maintaining compatibility with those under poorer conditions. TDM-PONs that allow ONUs to operate at varying peak data rates are referred to as flexible-rate PONs [12], and this concept is also under discussion in the ongoing work of ITU-T Study Group 15 (SG15) on Very High Speed PON [14].

In flexible-rate PONs, ONUs with similar channel conditions can be grouped to share the same transmission parameters, e.g., modulation formats and forward error correction (FEC) coding, enabling them to operate at a specific peak data rate. Furthermore, the peak data rate can be flexibly adjusted by modifying transmission parameters within the constraint of the power budget [11-20]. Upstream multi-rate reception is supported not only in multi-generation PON coexistence systems [21,22], but also natively in advanced standards such as NG-PON2 and 50G-PON [4,5]. Since the OLT can receive data encoded with different modulation formats, the traditional upstream scheduling protocol can still be used after introducing flexible rates [23]. Notably, the differences in peak data rates among ONUs must be considered during time slot allocation to ensure efficient scheduling [15,24]. In contrast, in the downstream direction, since ONUs may employ different transmission parameters, the traditional broadcast-based

downstream scheduling protocol in the fixed-rate PON becomes ineffective. To address this, the downstream PHY frame is divided into multiple subframes, each occupying multiple specific time slots [10,16]. The subframe differs in modulation and coding parameters, which are assigned to a group of ONUs with similar channel conditions and data rate requirements. Different from fixed-rate PONs, where ONUs need to process the whole downstream frame, ONUs in flexible-rate PON only receive and process their own downstream subframe to reduce computing complexity and energy consumption [10,18,25]. Compared to fixed-rate PONs, flexible-rate PONs have greater potential for improving throughput efficiency by exploiting available link margin. Moreover, they reduce power consumption and lower ONU computational complexity, thus are worthy of further investigation.

Despite these advantages, flexible-rate PONs still face several open issues, such as the challenge of maintaining stable downstream synchronization under flexible modulation, and the potential increase in system cost. Among these, downstream scheduling remains a key challenge, especially in multicast scenarios. On one hand, multicast scenarios introduce additional redundancy into the current scheduling mechanisms, thereby impacting system performance. The growing demand for high-bandwidth video services, e.g., live video streaming, personalized short-form videos, and ultra-high-definition video-on-demand services, has significantly increased multicast traffic, further straining scheduling efficiency [26,27]. Based on broadcast mode, downstream services can be classified into unicast and multicast services. Unicast services, e.g., the video-on-demand (VoD) streams, require dedicated data flows for individual user requests to ensure personalized content delivery. Thus, a unicast traffic flow is sent exclusively to its corresponding ONU in a fixed-rate PON. In contrast, a traffic flow from multicast service, e.g., live streaming, may be broadcast simultaneously to multiple ONUs. The set of ONU members associated with a specific multicast service is referred to as its multicast membership. Nowadays, multicast delivery has already been implemented in FTTx broadband access networks [28-30]. In GPON and EPON systems, the patching-based multicast mechanisms are commonly used: the first user initiates a multicast stream, and subsequent users receive the ongoing content via multicast and the missed portion through short unicast patches [28]. This method significantly reduces redundant transmissions and improves bandwidth utilization. Moreover, these multicast services often follow a Zipf distribution, where a small number of highly popular contents account for a large portion of total traffic. As a result, operators can pre-cache these popular contents in user-side buffers during off-peak hours, thereby improving delivery efficiency [29]. In addition, for live streaming scenarios, an SDN-aided NG-EPON architecture has been proposed to dynamically manage multicast groups based on user viewports and QoS demands [30]. However, in flexible-rate PONs, each ONU group can only process its own subframe. Consequently, when the memberships of a multicast service are distributed across multiple ONU groups, the multicast data must be duplicated and encapsulated into separate subframes. The amount of duplicated data increases with the number of ONU groups associated with the service, leading to significant redundancy and limiting effective throughput. A straightforward approach to reducing redundancy is to minimize the number of ONU groups. However, this may lower the data rates of ONUs with better channel conditions, which reduces the overall system capacity. Consequently, despite the decrease in redundancy, effective throughput may still degrade. Therefore, optimizing ONU grouping requires balancing the trade-off between minimizing redundancy and maintaining high data rates to maximize overall effective throughput.

On the other hand, in multicast scenarios, allocating downstream bandwidth to satisfy the bandwidth requirements of services with different broadcast modes introduces additional challenges. In [31], a session-based priority bandwidth allocation mechanism was proposed to dynamically allocate bandwidth among ONUs in TDM-PONs, addressing inefficiencies caused by multiple ONUs requesting the same multicast content. On this basis, [32] proposed a multicast-share weighted fair queuing (MS-WFQ) mechanism to target inter-session fairness, which dynamically adjusts the service weights of multicast services to optimize throughput while maintaining fairness across these services. However, such schemes are difficult to apply in flexible-rate PONs that employ ONU grouping methods, as they do not account for multicast redundancy and the varying data rates of ONUs. Consequently, they struggle to meet the requirements of services, which is crucial for maintaining high effective throughput in a flexible-rate PON. Therefore, downstream bandwidth allocation schemes should be enhanced to consider both multicast redundancy and data rate differences, thereby fully meeting service requirements and improving scheduling efficiency.

To address these challenges, this paper first enhances the downstream scheduling protocol for flexible-rate PON to support multicast scenarios. Given the limitations of existing ONU grouping and bandwidth allocation schemes, we introduce a novel downstream traffic-aware ONU grouping (TAOG) algorithm, complemented by a grouping-based downstream time slot allocation (GBDTA) algorithm. Simulation results show that the combination of the proposed algorithms, referred to as the TAOG-GBDTA scheme, can effectively support multicast scenarios and significantly improve system performance in terms of effective throughput and latency.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces an enhanced downstream scheduling protocol and analyzes the effective throughput for flexible-rate PON. Section 3 presents the proposed TAOG-GBDTA scheme based on the proposed scheduling protocol. Section 4 presents and analyzes the simulation results for the proposed algorithm. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. FLEXIBLE-RATE PON ARCHITECTURE AND PROTOCOL

In this section, we first present a representative architecture of a flexible-rate PON. To support dynamic ONU grouping in a multicast scenario, an enhanced downstream scheduling protocol is proposed. Then, we further analyze the downstream effective throughput in a flexible-rate PON.

A. Architecture

Fig. 1 illustrates the high-level architecture of a flexible-rate PON, which consists of an OLT and multiple ONUs. The ONUs adopt different transmission parameters, e.g., modulation format, according to their OPL, which is influenced by factors such as physical fiber distance and the number of optical splitters along the ODN. For example, ONU₁ in Fig. 1, is connected to the OLT via a single optical splitter, thus experiencing a low OPL, which enables utilizing the 4-level pulse amplitude modulation (PAM4) format to achieve higher data rates. In contrast, ONU₂ and ONU₃ are connected via two optical splitters, hence experiencing a higher OPL. Therefore, they employ the non-return-to-zero (NRZ) modulation format to maintain reliable performance under more challenging channel conditions. Based on their OPL, these ONUs are grouped into two groups: ONU₁ belongs to Group 1, while ONU₂ and ONU₃ belong to Group 2. However, the data rates for these ONUs can be adjusted dynamically, and the group assignments may change accordingly. To support this flexibility, digital signal processing (DSP) modules are introduced in both the OLT and the ONUs, enabling modulation format adaptation during transmission and reception. The operation of the DSP modules is managed by the PON transmission convergence (TC) layer, which consists of the service adaptation sublayer, framing sublayer, and PHY adaptation sublayer. These sublayers handle framing, scheduling, and group management, among others.

Fig. 1 High-level architecture of flexible-rate PON.

In the downstream transmission, the OLT divides the frame into multiple forward error correction (FEC) codewords, i.e., data blocks encoded with FEC for error resilience, customized for different ONU groups. For instance, FEC codewords modulated with PAM4 are designated for Group 1, while those modulated with NRZ are directed to Group 2. Upon receiving the downstream frame, each ONU identifies the FEC codewords corresponding to its modulation format and reconstructs its assigned subframe. For example, Group 1 only processes the PAM4-modulated codewords (yellow blocks), while Group 2 processes the NRZ-modulated codewords (green blocks). This ensures that each ONU group handles only its designated data, thereby reducing DSP complexity.

The flexible-rate PON architecture determines a special downstream scheduling scheme that is distinct from that of conventional fixed-rate PONs. Downstream scheduling protocol plays a critical role in implementing dynamic ONU grouping, especially in multicast scenarios. In the next subsection, we introduce the downstream scheduling protocol for fixed-rate PONs, followed by our proposed enhanced downstream scheduling protocol tailored for flexible-rate PONs.

B. Enhanced downstream scheduling protocol

Fig. 2(a) illustrates the downstream scheduling protocol according to the ITU-T 50G-PON Common TC layer specification [5]. In the OLT, service data units (SDU), such as Ethernet frames, are first classified and added to different queues based on their service types (step 1). Then, in the service adaptation sublayer, SDUs are encapsulated into XGEM frames using an XG-PON encapsulation method and assigned a Port-ID, which is included in the header (step 2). The XGEM Port-ID identifies its corresponding service type and broadcast mode. The XGEM Port-ID of a unicast XGEM frame corresponds to a single ONU, whereas the XGEM Port-ID of a multicast XGEM frame can be recognized by multiple ONUs. For illustrative purposes, Fig. 2(a) shows three multicast (M_1 , M_2 , and M_3) and two unicast (U_1 and U_2) traffic flows belonging to different services. Among these, M_3 is broadcast to all ONUs. It represents a special traffic type that can broadcast configuration and management information to every ONU, e.g., the ONU Management and Control Interface (OMCI) messages. Multicast XGEM frames are marked with dashed-line blocks, while the unicast XGEM frames are represented by solid-line blocks. As a result, all multicast XGEM frames need to be transmitted only once, and therefore, each service requires one single dedicated time slot.

In the framing sublayer, a bandwidth allocation module allocates downstream bandwidth to each traffic, determining the XGEM frames that need to be scheduled (step 3). As per the bandwidth allocation information, the traffic scheduler aggregates these XGEM frames and encapsulates them into an FS frame by adding an FS header (step 4). The FS header contains both the upstream bandwidth allocation information (i.e., the BWmap field) and the downstream physical layer operation, administration, and maintenance (PLOAMd) field for ONUs. The PLOAMd messages account for carrying management and control instructions for ONUs, such as ONU activation or ranging. Since a multicast XGEM frame can be recognized by multiple ONUs, each multicast traffic (M_1 , M_2 and M_3) is allocated one single dedicated time slot in an FS frame. Subsequently, in the PHY adaptation sublayer, this FS frame is further encapsulated into a 125- μ s downstream PHY frame after FEC encoding, scrambling, and bit interleaving (step 5). After adding a downstream physical synchronization block (PSBd), the downstream PHY frame is broadcast to all ONUs in the flexible-rate PON. Upon receiving the PHY frame, each ONU synchronizes with the PSBd field and extracts the FS frame (step 6). The FS frame is then further de-encapsulated into XGEM frames at the framing sublayer, where the BWmap fields are extracted from the FS header and utilized by the ONU for upstream scheduling (step 7). A traffic classifier then categorizes the data frames and selects its corresponding XGEM frames based on the XGEM Port-IDs, restoring them into SDUs in the service adaptation sublayer (step 8). Notably, in this protocol, every ONU must receive and process the entire downstream PHY frame.

Fig. 2 (a) Downstream scheduling protocol in a fixed-rate PON, (b) enhanced downstream scheduling protocol in a flexible-rate PON.

In contrast to the fixed-rate PON, the downstream scheduling protocol in a flexible-rate PON must account for the varying transmission parameters across ONU groups. Noted that to avoid potential detection errors and limit DSP complexity, in this paper, each ONU is restricted to belong to only one group at a time in a flexible-rate PON. Consequently, data for different ONU groups are independently encapsulated according to their respective transmission parameters. To achieve this, after processing in the service adaptation sublayer, XGEM frames belonging to the same ONU group are aggregated and encapsulated into an independent FS frame. For multicast traffic, if all its ONU members belong to the same group, the corresponding FS frame can directly carry its multicast XGEM frames without duplication. Otherwise, the XGEM frames must be duplicated and encapsulated into n FS frames, where n represents the number of ONU groups spanned by the multicast service. This implies that a multicast service will be assigned a different time slot in multiple distinct FS frames. Fig. 2(b) illustrates the enhanced downstream scheduling protocol to support multicast scenarios. Assume that ONU₁ belongs to Group 1, ONU₂ and ONU₃ belong to another group. The multicast XGEM frame M_1 is intended for ONU₁ and ONU₂, and M_3 is received by all ONUs. Therefore, M_1 and M_3 are both duplicated and encapsulated into FS Frame 1 and FS Frame 2 (step 4). In contrast, multicast traffic 2 has ONU members ONU₂ and ONU₃ in the same group, and thus M_2 is only encapsulated into FS Frame 2. Noted that the duplication of XGEM frames occurs only during the encapsulation into FS frames. As a result, no additional queues are required in the OLT to store data frames for different groups, eliminating the need for modifying the queue management mechanism. Since ONU grouping is determined by transmission parameters, regular updates of these parameters are necessary to support dynamic ONU grouping. To achieve this, each FS frame includes the transmission parameter information within the PLOAMd field for the ONUs of the group periodically. This information, together with the BWmap, is generated by a novel ONU grouping and bandwidth allocation module (step 3) and copied to all FS frame headers by the traffic scheduler to ensure consistent updates across all ONU groups (step 4). We prefer PLOAMd field rather than OMCI for delivering grouping updates, as PLOAM messages offer lower signaling latency, thereby enabling prompt ONU reconfiguration. The FS frames from different groups are subsequently aggregated in the PHY adaptation sublayer and encapsulated into a complete downstream PHY frame (step 5). During this process, a codeword interleaving method between FS frames can be performed to reduce DSP complexity [25]. Upon receiving the downstream PHY frame, the ONU reconstructs the FS frame for its group (step 6). Subsequently, the FS frame is de-encapsulated at the framing sublayer (step 7). In addition to the BWmap field used for upstream scheduling, the PLOAMd field in the FS header provides

Fig. 3 Examples of a downstream PHY frame in (a) a fixed-rate PON, (b) a flexible-rate PON, and (c) a flexible-rate PON with ONU grouping optimization.

updated transmission parameters. To enable dynamic ONU grouping, the ONU uses this information to adjust its modulation format for receiving downstream data. Meanwhile, the extracted XGEM frames are processed at the service adaptation sublayer (step 8), where the traffic classifier determines whether the frames are intended for the receiving ONU.

C. Downstream effective throughput analysis

To evaluate the potential performance improvements brought by dynamic group optimization, we further analyze the downstream effective throughput under three different ONU grouping methods: a) a fixed-rate PON; b) a flexible-rate PON; and c) a flexible-rate PON with ONU grouping optimization.

Fig. 3(a) illustrates an example of a downstream PHY frame in a fixed-rate PON without ONU grouping. For simplicity, the overhead is omitted. The colored blocks represent the bandwidth allocated to different services, which is determined by a fixed data rate r_0 and frame duration t_0 . U_j^i and M_j^i indicate the j^{th} unicast and multicast service targeting ONU i , respectively. Suppose that there are six ONUs and five traffic flows (from four unicast services and one multicast service) that require transmission. Since both unicast and multicast data are transmitted only once, no redundancy is generated. In this scenario, the downstream effective throughput equals the sum of bandwidth allocated to each service.

Fig. 3(b) presents an example of a downstream PHY frame in a flexible-rate PON with a fixed ONU grouping method. In this case, the system achieves its maximum system capacity. Six ONUs are divided into three groups: Group 1, Group 2, and Group 3. ONU1 and ONU2 in Group 1 achieve the highest data rate r_1 due to favorable channel conditions, while ONU3 and ONU4 in Group 2 operate at a lower peak data rate r_2 . The ONU5 and ONU6 in Group 3 experience the poorest channel conditions and operate at the lowest peak data rate $r_3 = r_0$. Assuming the FS frame of each group is allocated an equal time slot duration (i.e., $t_1 = t_2 = t_3$), the flexible-rate PON can transmit the same data in less time (indicated by the red dashed blocks), thereby increasing the maximum system throughput. However, the multicast data M_1 directed to ONUs in three different groups (i.e., ONU1, ONU4, and ONU6) must be transmitted separately for each group, occupying up to three time slots (M_1^1 , M_1^4 , and M_1^6), which introduces unnecessary redundancy and significantly reduces the effective throughput.

Fig. 3(c) shows an example after optimizing the grouping by moving ONU4 from Group 2 to Group 3 (i.e., lowering its data rate to r_3), so the redundant transmission M_1^4 can be eliminated. Compared to the solution in Fig. 3(b), this adjustment further improves the effective throughput. However, moving ONU1 to Group 3 to further reduce redundancy is not advisable, as lowering its data rate would increase the time slot required for the unicast service U_1^1 , thus decreasing the overall effective throughput. Therefore, optimizing ONU grouping involves a trade-off between minimizing redundancy and maintaining high ONU data rates.

Furthermore, considering that not only the multicast traffic load but also multicast memberships can dynamically change as ONUs join or leave a multicast session, it is necessary to design a traffic-aware algorithm to optimize ONU grouping dynamically. In addition, the examples in Figs. 3(b) and 3(c) adopt a simple bandwidth allocation strategy where bandwidth is evenly allocated among ONU groups. In practice, downstream bandwidth allocation in flexible-rate PONs is more complex and can significantly impact the system effective throughput. To address this, the next section proposes a scheme that integrates optimized ONU grouping with an advanced downstream bandwidth allocation algorithm.

3. TRAFFIC-AWARE ONU GROUPING AND DOWNSTREAM BANDWIDTH ALLOCATION

Based on the proposed downstream scheduling protocol, we further design a TAOG-GBDTA scheme combined by two heuristic algorithms for flexible-rate PONs. Fig. 4 shows the TAOG-GBDTA framework in the TC layer of OLT. In this framework, the proposed TAOG algorithm and GBDTA algorithm optimize the ONU grouping and downstream bandwidth allocation, respectively.

As shown in Fig. 4, both the TAOG and GBDTA algorithms receive traffic parameters from the multicast information manager module in the upper layer during each *scheduling cycle*, which has a fixed length of 125 μ s. These parameters include the traffic load of services and the mapping table between services and their multicast memberships. Based on these parameters, the TAOG algorithm periodically generates optimized ONU groupings, which are fed into the GBDTA algorithm and provided to the traffic scheduler for generating PLOAMd messages. The interval between these updates is referred to as an *optimization cycle*, which is set as an integer multiple of the scheduling cycle. Noted that the optimization cycle is configurable and can be set significantly longer than the scheduling cycle to match hardware constraints and ensure enough time for ONUs to switch groups via PLOAMd-based updates. In Fig. 4, blue arrows indicate the inputs and outputs that occur at each scheduling cycle, while green arrows represent those at each optimization cycle. The GBDTA algorithm is responsible for performing downstream bandwidth allocation. When a new ONU grouping is provided, GBDTA updates the relevant parameters accordingly to ensure optimal bandwidth allocation decisions. The output decisions are fed into the traffic scheduler to generate FS frames for each ONU group. The detailed descriptions of these two algorithms are provided in the following subsections.

Fig. 4 TAOG-GBDTA framework.

A. Traffic-aware ONU grouping

The TAOG algorithm is designed to iteratively optimize ONU grouping in response to time-varying network conditions, thereby improving the effective throughput. Specifically, the algorithm begins with an initial ONU grouping, i.e., the currently adopted ONU grouping, and explores new ONU groupings by making incremental adjustments, i.e., reassigning one ONU to a different group or modifying its data rate. At each step, the algorithm evaluates whether the new solution can improve system effective throughput by an acceptance threshold. As the algorithm progresses, the threshold gradually decreases, making it increasingly selective and ultimately converging on an optimized grouping solution. The TAOG algorithm is detailed as follows.

At the beginning of each scheduling cycle, traffic-related parameters are updated. Let Λ , Ω , and Γ denote the sets of all services, ONUs, and groups, respectively. Both unicast and multicast services are included in Λ , as a unicast service can be considered a special multicast case with a single ONU member. For each service $i \in \Lambda$, the newly arrived traffic in the previous scheduling cycle is denoted by d_i , and the cumulative traffic load from the end of the last optimization cycle to the present moment is denoted by p_i . These parameters are collectively represented by vectors $D = [d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{N^S}]$ and $P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{N^S}]$, respectively, where N^S represents the total number of services. \mathbb{P} is updated as $(\mathbb{P} + \mathbb{D})$ during each scheduling cycle. Besides, the multicast membership of each service is updated using the multicast management messages received by the OLT, such as the Internet group management protocol (IGMP) JOIN/LEAVE messages [33]. We assume that by the time the OLT updates its multicast membership table, the IGMP signaling process has already completed and thus does not affect ONU grouping decisions. The mapping table between services and their multicast memberships can be described as a matrix \mathbb{M} , defined as

$$\mathbb{M} = \begin{bmatrix} m_{1,1} & m_{1,2} & \dots & m_{1,N^O} \\ m_{2,1} & m_{2,2} & \dots & m_{2,N^O} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ m_{N^S,1} & m_{N^S,2} & \dots & m_{N^S,N^O} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where N^O denotes the total number of ONUs, and $m_{i,j} \in \{0,1\}$ indicates whether ONU j is a member of service i . Specifically, $m_{i,j} = 1$ indicates that ONU j is a member of service i , and $m_{i,j} = 0$ otherwise. Similarly, the current ONU grouping is described by a matrix \mathbb{G}^C , expressed as

$$\mathbb{G}^C = \begin{bmatrix} g_{1,1} & g_{1,2} & \dots & g_{1,N^G} \\ g_{2,1} & g_{2,2} & \dots & g_{2,N^G} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ g_{N^O,1} & g_{N^O,2} & \dots & g_{N^O,N^G} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where N^G denotes the number of groups, and $g_{j,k} \in \{0,1\}$ indicates whether ONU j belongs to group k (i.e., $g_{j,k} = 1$ means ONU j belongs to group k , and $g_{j,k} = 0$ otherwise). As mentioned in Section 2, each ONU is assumed to belong to only one group at a time. Accordingly, each ONU is restricted to a single group during the optimization, and $g_{i,k}$ must satisfy

$$\sum_{k \in \Gamma} g_{j,k} = 1, \quad j \in \Omega \quad (3)$$

Then, the OLT checks an internal countdown timer τ , which tracks the remaining scheduling cycles before the next grouping optimization. If $\tau = 1$, the optimization process is triggered, and τ is reset to τ^G , which denotes the predefined optimization cycle. Otherwise, τ is decremented by one, and the algorithm terminates for this scheduling cycle. During grouping optimization, the performance of the current grouping G^C is evaluated. For this, a matrix $\mathbb{L} = [l_{i,k}]$ is generated, expressed as

$$\mathbb{L} = \mathbb{M}\mathbb{G}^C, \quad (4)$$

where the element $l_{i,k}$ indicates the number of ONU members of service i in group k . In the enhanced downstream scheduling protocol, the ONU members of a service belonging to the same group share the same time slot, and the redundancy occurs when ONU members are from different groups. To account for shared time slots, each $l_{i,k}$ in \mathbb{L} is transformed into $l'_{i,k}$, thus a new matrix \mathbb{L}' is generated. $l'_{i,k}$ is calculated by

$$l'_{i,k} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } l_{i,k} \geq 1 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $l'_{i,k}$ indicates whether service i has any ONU members in group k . \mathbb{L}' is then used to calculate the total traffic load and redundancy for each service, which is denoted by a vector $\mathbb{B} = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{N^G}]$ and expressed as

$$\mathbb{B} = \mathbb{P}\mathbb{L}'. \quad (6)$$

Let the vector $\mathbb{R} = [r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{N^G}]$ denotes the data rates of the ONU groups. Using \mathbb{B} and \mathbb{R} , the total time slots for group k in the last optimization cycle are calculated as (b_k/r_k) . Furthermore, the effective throughput under the current ONU grouping G^C in the last optimization cycle, referred to as ET^C , is expressed as

$$ET^C = \frac{\sum_{i \in \Lambda} P_i}{\sum_{k \in \Gamma} \frac{b_k}{r_k}} \quad (7)$$

Noted that the numerator, which represents the total amount of accumulated traffic to be served, is fixed during each optimization cycle, while the denominator reflects the total time required to serve this traffic under the current ONU grouping G^C . Therefore, the optimization on effective throughput can be formulated by minimizing the denominator, referred to as the effective service time (ES^C).

To minimize the effective service time ES^C , an optimized grouping solution G^B should be found. To achieve this, the algorithm follows an iterative process to explore potential solutions, and the number of iterations is determined by I^{max} . ES^C and G^C are initially set to the minimum effective service time ES^B and the optimal ONU grouping solution G^B , respectively. At each iteration, a new ONU grouping solution G^N is generated based on G^C by randomly selecting an ONU and adjusting its data rate up or down by one level. Noted that the adjustment should not exceed the peak data rate constraint of the ONU. The new effective service time ES^N under G^N is then calculated by Eqs. (4)-(7). The difference in effective service time, referred to as δ , is expressed as

Algorithm 1: Traffic-aware ONU grouping (TAOG) algorithm

Input: $\tau^G, \tau, AT, I^{max}, \gamma, \Lambda, \Omega, \Gamma, \mathbb{D}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{M}, \mathbb{G}^C, \mathbb{R}$

Output: G^B

1. $\mathbb{P} \leftarrow \mathbb{P} + \mathbb{D}$
 2. **if** $\tau > 1$ **then**
 3. $\tau \leftarrow \tau - 1$
 4. **elseif** $\tau == 1$ **then**
 5. $\tau \leftarrow \tau^G$
 6. Calculate \mathbb{L}' and \mathbb{B} by Eqs. (4)-(6)
 7. Calculate ES^C by Eq. (7)
 8. $G^B \leftarrow G^C; ES^B \leftarrow ES^C$
 9. **while** $i \leq I^{max}$ **do**
 10. Generate a new solution G^N
 11. Calculate ES^N based on G^N
 12. $\delta \leftarrow ES^N - ES^C$
 13. **if** $\delta < 0$ **then**
 14. $G^C \leftarrow G^N; ES^C \leftarrow ES^N$
 15. **else**
 16. $P_A \leftarrow \exp(-\delta/AT)$
 17. Generate Y
 18. **if** $P_A > Y$ **then**
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19.       $\mathbb{G}^C \leftarrow \mathbb{G}^N; ES^C \leftarrow ES^N$ 
20.      end if
21.      end if
22.      if  $ES^C < ES^B$  then
23.           $\mathbb{G}^B \leftarrow \mathbb{G}^C; ES^B \leftarrow ES^C$ 
24.      end if
25.       $AT \leftarrow AT \cdot \gamma$ 
26.       $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
27.      end while
28.      Reset  $\mathbb{P}$ 
29.      end if

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$$\delta = ES^N - ES^C. \quad (8)$$

If $\delta < 0$, \mathbb{G}^N is accepted as the new current solution. Otherwise, the acceptance of \mathbb{G}^N is determined probabilistically using the acceptance probability P_A , which can be written as

$$P_A = e^{-\frac{\delta}{AT}}, \quad (9)$$

where AT denotes the acceptance threshold. A higher initial AT allows the algorithm to explore a wider solution space by increasing the probability of accepting suboptimal solutions, whereas a lower AT results in a more conservative search. To determine whether \mathbb{G}^N is accepted, P_A is then compared against a random value Y ranging from 0 and 1. If $P_A > Y$, \mathbb{G}^N is accepted; otherwise, it retains \mathbb{G}^C . Following this, AT is reduced according to $(AT = \gamma \cdot AT)$, where γ is the decay factor controlling the rate of reduction. A higher γ ensures a slower decay and more thorough exploration, while a lower γ accelerates convergence but risks getting trapped in a local optimum. At the end of each iteration, the best-known solution \mathbb{G}^B is updated if ES^C is smaller than the previously recorded ES^B ; otherwise, \mathbb{G}^B remains unchanged.

After completing the iterations, the best solution \mathbb{G}^B is selected based on the minimum observed effective service time. The elements in \mathbb{P} are reset to zero for the next optimization cycle. Finally, \mathbb{G}^B is passed to the GBDTA algorithm and the traffic scheduler for downstream bandwidth allocation and traffic scheduling.

The pseudo-code for the proposed TAOG algorithm is shown in Algorithm 1. Steps (1-5) check whether grouping optimization is required in the current scheduling cycle. In steps (6-8), the effective service time for the current ONU grouping in the last optimization cycle is calculated and temporarily set as the optimal solution. Following this, steps (9-26) try to find an optimized ONU grouping solution by iteration. Steps (10-11) generate a new grouping solution, and steps (12-21) determine whether to accept the new solution. Steps (22-24) compare the new solution with the current optimal solution and update the optimal solution accordingly. Afterward, the algorithm reduces its acceptance threshold (step 25) and iterates again. Finally, P is reset in step (28).

B. Grouping-based downstream time slot allocation

The GBDTA algorithm is proposed to optimize the downstream bandwidth allocation in multicast scenarios, thereby further maximizing the effective throughput of the flexible-rate PON. Here, bandwidth specifically refers to the time slots allocated for data transmission.

First, the OLT calculates the length of the available time slots for the entire downstream PHY frame (T) before the beginning of each scheduling cycle, which can be expressed as

$$T = E - T^{PSBd} - T^{FS} - T^P, \quad (10)$$

where E denotes the total duration of a downstream PHY frame, T^{PSBd} denotes the time slots occupied by the PSBd, T^{FS} accounts for the time slots used for FS headers, and T^P represents the time slots allocated for parity bits in the FEC codewords. Simultaneously, if the TAOG algorithm has generated a new ONU grouping solution, \mathbb{G}^C is updated. The matrix \mathbb{M} , which reflects the multicast memberships of services, is also updated based on the latest network conditions. Whenever either \mathbb{G}^C or \mathbb{M} is updated, \mathbb{L}' is recalculated using Eqs. (4) and (5).

Subsequently, the OLT allocates downstream time slots to each service. To prevent the overuse of downstream bandwidth by any single service due to the variation of the bandwidth demand, each service must be allocated a maximum available time slot. Here, the maximum available time slot of service i is determined by its bandwidth weight ω_i , which is defined as the ratio of the required time slot for service i to the total required time slots for all services, expressed as

$$\omega_i = \frac{TS_i^{Req}}{\sum_{n \in \Lambda} TS_n^{Req}}, \quad (11)$$

where TS_i^{Req} denotes the requested time slot of service i . For a multicast service, more than one time slot may be required in different FS frames, where different modulation formats are applied during transmission. Thus, TS_i^{Req} is expressed as

$$TS_i^{Req} = \sum_{k \in \Gamma} l'_{i,k} \frac{d_i}{r_k}. \quad (12)$$

Based on ω_i , the maximum available time slot for service i can be obtained by $(\omega_i T)$. If the required TS_i^{Req} can be accommodated within this limit, it is allocated as requested; otherwise, it is limited to $(\omega_i T)$. The total time slot allocated to service i , i.e., TS_i^{Ser} , is expressed as

$$TS_i^{Ser} = \begin{cases} TS_i^{Req}, & \text{if } TS_i^{Req} \leq \omega_i T \\ \omega_i T, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (13)$$

Following this, TS_i^{Ser} for each service is further divided and incorporated into multiple FS frames of its associated ONU groups. The time slot allocated to group k for service i , denoted as $TS_{i,k}^{Gro}$, can be calculated as

$$TS_{i,k}^{Gro} = \sigma_{i,k} \cdot TS_i^{Ser}, \quad (14)$$

where $\sigma_{i,k}$ represents the bandwidth weight assigned to group k for service i . For a multicast service, the data encapsulated in each FS frame is identical in size, while the time slot length varies depending on the data rate of the group. Therefore, $\sigma_{i,k}$ is expressed as

$$\sigma_{i,k} = \frac{l'_{i,k}}{r_k \sum_{n \in \Gamma} \frac{l'_{i,n}}{r_n}}. \quad (15)$$

Since each ONU in the group can independently identify its own data frames by recognizing the XGEM header, $TS_{i,k}^{Gro}$ can be shared among the ONU members in the group and there is no need for further division at the ONU level. Finally, the traffic scheduler generates the FS frame for each group based on $TS_{i,k}^{Gro}$.

The pseudo-code of the GBDTA algorithm is detailed in Algorithm 2. Step (1) updates the parameters. Step (2) calculates the maximum available time slot for each service. In steps (3-10), the algorithm allocates time slots to services based on their demands. Subsequently, the time slots allocated to each group are calculated in steps (11). Finally, in step (14), FS frames are generated based on the allocated time slots for each group.

The computational complexity of TAOG-GBDTA is analyzed as follows. The complexity of the TAOG algorithm depends on the number of iterations. For the GBDTA algorithm, its complexity is determined by the number of services and their corresponding groups, expressed as $O(|A| \cdot |\Gamma|)$. Given that conventional bandwidth allocation algorithms in flexible-rate PONs also assign time slots to each group associated with a service, the time complexity remains unchanged. Therefore, the primary source of complexity increase in the proposed scheme mainly stems from the optimization of ONU grouping.

Algorithm 2: Grouping-based downstream time slot allocation
(GBDTA) algorithm

Input: $E, T^{PSBd}, T^{FS}, T^P, \Lambda, \Omega, \Gamma, M, \mathbb{G}^C, \mathbb{D}, \mathbb{R}$
Output: $TS_{i,k}^{Gro}$

1. $T \leftarrow E - T^{PSBd} - T^{FS} - T^P$
2. Update \mathbb{L}' by Eqs. (4)-(5)
3. **for** $i \in \Lambda$ **do**
4. Calculate TS_i^{Req} and ω_i by Eqs. (11)-(12)
5. **if** $TS_i^{Req} \leq \omega_i T$
6. $TS_i^{Ser} \leftarrow TS_i^{Req}$
7. **else**
8. $TS_i^{Ser} \leftarrow \omega_i T$
9. **end if**
10. **for** $k \in \Gamma$ **do**
11. Calculate $\sigma_{i,k}$ and $TS_{i,k}^{Gro}$ by Eqs. (14)-(15)
12. **end for**
13. **end for**
14. Generate downstream FS frames based on $TS_{i,k}^{Gro}$

4. SIMULATION AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluate the performances of our proposed TAOG-GBDTA scheme compared against two benchmarks. In Benchmark 1, each ONU operates at its maximum available peak data rate, while in Benchmark 2, all ONUs are configured to operate at the lowest available data rate (i.e., 25 Gb/s) throughout the simulation. For bandwidth allocation, both benchmarks use a classic multicast scheduling mechanism, i.e., the multicast sharing-based weighted fair queuing (MS-WFQ) mechanism [27]. For this, we develop a simulator in MATLAB, which incorporates our enhanced downstream scheduling protocol to simulate the downstream scheduling procedures in a flexible-rate PON.

A. Simulation conditions

Our simulation considers a flexible-rate PON system with a varying number of ONUs: 16, 32, and 64. The ONUs are initially divided into four groups based on their available peak data rates, which correspond to 25 Gb/s, 50 Gb/s, 75 Gb/s, and 100 Gb/s, respectively. This rate combination can be achieved by the fine-granularity rate control demonstrated in [16]. The physical distance of each ONU follows a Gaussian distribution, where the mean is 15 km and the variance is 64 km. The physical distance of each ONU is directly mapped to each ONU's peak data rate using a simplified rule: distances between 5 and 10 km correspond to 100 Gb/s, between 10 and 15 km to 75 Gb/s, between 15 and 20 km to 50 Gb/s, and distances greater than 20 km

to 25 Gb/s. The downstream traffic consists of 8 unicast and 8 multicast services, each modeled as a typical Internet protocol television stream. The packet arrival times follow a Poisson distribution, with all services sharing the same average packet arrival rate. Each service has a minimum traffic rate of 10 Mbit/s, where the XGEM frame size is 1324 bytes including an 8-byte XGEM header [5,29]. Additionally, a lightweight OMCI service is also considered to reflect real PON operation, which includes periodic Management Information Base (MIB) Upload and performance monitoring (PM) reports. Specifically, the OLT broadcasts a 56-byte MIB Upload request (including an 8-byte header) every 30 seconds [32]. The OMCI service is broadcast to all ONUs. The buffer size of each service queue is set to 20 MB. Furthermore, the arrivals of multicast JOIN and LEAVE requests (i.e., the request messages to join or leave the multicast membership of a service sent by ONUs) also follow a Poisson distribution [26-28]. The number of multicast requests for each multicast service follows a Zipf distribution. Zipf distribution is commonly used to model multimedia access patterns and reflects the dynamic changes in multicast memberships [26,27]. The request probability for multicast service i , denoted by RP_i , is expressed as

$$RP_i = \frac{C}{i^\alpha}, \quad i \in \Lambda \quad (16)$$

where α determines the long-tail behavior of the distribution. In our simulation, α is set to 1 to closely reflect typical multicast access patterns [26,27]. The normalization constant C is defined as

Parameter	Value
Number of ONUs	16, 32, 64
Available data rates	25 Gb/s, 50 Gb/s, 75 Gb/s, 100 Gb/s (mapped based on ONU distance) [16]
Physical distance	Gaussian, mean: 15; variance: 64
Downstream services	8 unicast, 8 multicast, and 1 broadcast (OMCI) service
Traffic model	Unicast and multicast: Poisson; OMCI: periodic
Packet size	Unicast and multicast: 1324 bytes; OMCI: 56 bytes
Minimum service rate	10 Mb/s
ONU buffer size	20 MBytes
Multicast membership	Zipf distribution ($\alpha=1$)
Optimization cycle	12.5 ms
Optimization parameters	Acceptance threshold: 150; decay factor: 0.99; Max iterations: 10,000

$$C = \frac{1}{\sum_{i \in \Lambda} \frac{1}{i^\alpha}}. \quad (17)$$

In the proposed TAOG-GBDTA scheme, the optimization cycle is set to 100 scheduling cycles, i.e., 12.5 ms. The initial acceptance threshold and the decay factor are set to 150 and 0.99, respectively. Without loss of generality, the maximum number of iterations is set to 10,000 to balance computational efficiency and throughput performance [30-32]. Additionally, all ONUs utilize the same FEC scheme with a coding rate of 0.8444 [4,5]. Each simulation is repeated ten times for every scheduling scheme under each traffic load, with each run emulating one second of system operation. The confidence level is 95%. The main parameters of the simulation are detailed in Table 1.

B. Performance evaluation

In this subsection, we first investigate the impact of the number of ONUs on effective throughput performance, as larger ONU scales could lead to increased multicast redundancy. We then analyze the ONU grouping decisions of the TAOG-GBDTA schemes compared with the benchmarks under dynamic network conditions. For this, we examine two key metrics: the total group count and the average data rate of all ONUs. Here, the total group count refers to the accumulated number of group entries across all multicast services. If a multicast service is delivered to ONUs located in multiple groups, each involved group is counted once per service. The average data rate refers to the mean of adopted data rates of all ONUs. Both metrics are measured at the end of each optimization cycle. Following this, to further analyze the impact of ONU grouping and bandwidth allocation on system performances, we evaluate the effective throughput and redundancy under three different multicast traffic ratios (i.e., the ratio of multicast traffic rate to the total offered traffic rate): 25%, 50%, and 75%. Additionally, average packet delay and effective throughput are closely related, thus we also present the latency performance of each scheme under these three scenarios. These metrics are obtained as follows: Effective throughput and redundancy are computed by dividing the accumulated delivery and duplication volumes by the simulation time. Latency is computed as the average across all successfully delivered packets.

Fig. 5 Effective throughput versus offered traffic rate under different ONU scales ($N^O=16, 32,$ and 64) when the multicast ratio is 50%.

Fig. 6 Variation in (a) total group count and (b) average data rate when the multicast traffic ratio is 50% and offered traffic rate is 40 Gb/s.

1. Effective throughput and redundancy

We first investigate the impact of the number of ONUs on the effective throughput performance. Fig. 5 presents the effective throughput achieved under three ONU scales ($N^O = 16, 32,$ and 64) when the multicast traffic ratio is 50%. The offered traffic rate refers to the aggregate traffic load from all services in the system. When the offered traffic rate is low (from 5 to 15 Gb/s), all three schemes achieve similar effective throughput regardless of the ONU scale. This is because the system has sufficient bandwidth to accommodate the traffic demand, and redundancy has not become a bottleneck. As the offered traffic rate increases, performance differences gradually emerge. For Benchmark 2, all three curves ($N^O = 16, 32,$ and 64) nearly overlap,

which indicates that the number of ONUs has limited impact on its performance. This is expected, as all ONUs operate at the same fixed data rate and each multicast service is delivered through a single group, so increasing the number of ONUs does not introduce additional redundancy. However, Benchmark 1 shows a noticeable decline as the number of ONUs increases. For $N^o = 16$, Benchmark 1 achieves an effective throughput of approximately 19.89 Gb/s when the traffic rate reaches 50 Gb/s. However, it drops to 18.06 Gb/s for $N^o = 32$, and further declines to 14.14 Gb/s for $N^o = 64$. This is because with more ONUs operating at their peak rates, multicast traffic becomes increasingly fragmented across groups, leading to higher redundancy. Furthermore, while the total system throughput already saturated under high-load conditions, redundant data becomes even more significant, particularly for $N^o = 32$ and 64. In such cases, the bandwidth allocation scheme in Benchmark 1

Fig. 7 Effective throughput versus offered traffic rate in the multicast traffic ratio of (a) 25%, (b) 50%, and (c) 75%; Redundancy versus offered traffic rate in the multicast traffic ratio of (d) 25%, (e) 50%, and (f) 75%.

further allows redundancy to crowd out the effective throughput. In contrast, the proposed TAOG-GBDTA scheme experiences only a slight throughput degradation as ONU number increases. At an offered traffic rate of 50Gb/s, its effective throughput decreases from 26.29 Gb/s ($N^o = 16$) to 25.15 Gb/s ($N^o = 32$), and 24.28 Gb/s ($N^o = 64$), respectively. This is because TAOG-GBDTA can dynamically control redundancy through adaptive ONU grouping, which limits the throughput degradation caused by fragmented ONU grouping.

To further illustrate how TAOG-GBDTA scheme contributes to the ONU grouping, we examine the two metrics, i.e., the total group count and the average data rate, in a case with a multicast traffic ratio of 50% and an offered traffic rate of 40 Gb/s. For simplicity, the following results are presented for a 16-ONU configuration. We first evaluate the total group count, as it directly reflects the multicast redundancy. Fig. 6(a) shows the variation in the total group count over 50 optimization cycles for three schemes. Benchmark 2 constantly has the lowest total group count because all ONUs operate at a uniform data rate and each multicast service is associated with only one group. For TAOG-GBDTA and Benchmark 1, they initially exhibit similar total group count since all ONUs operate at their highest available data rates. However, from the start of the first optimization cycle, the total group count of TAOG-GBDTA reduces rapidly by dynamically optimizing the ONU grouping. While the total group count fluctuates due to ongoing network changes, it consistently remains lower than Benchmark 1. Specifically, TAOG-GBDTA achieves an average total group count of 14.69, which is 44.5% lower than that of Benchmark 1 with an average of 26.47. This is due to that TAOG-GBDTA can significantly reduce redundant data transmissions for multicast services.

Next, we evaluate the average data rate, which is crucial for estimating system capacity. Fig. 6(b) compares the average data rate performance of TAOG-GBDTA and Benchmark 2 over the same optimization cycles. In Benchmark 2, the average data rate remains fixed at 25 Gb/s, because all ONUs operate at the lowest data rate. In contrast, Benchmark 1 consistently achieves the highest average data rate among the three, as it configures all ONUs to operate at their maximum data rates. TAOG-GBDTA, on the other hand, achieves an average value of approximately 48.65 Gb/s, reaching 69.1% of Benchmark 1 and nearly doubling that of Benchmark 2. This performance is attributed to its ability to maintain higher data rates to ONUs to minimize the transmission time for unicast services.

To further analyze the trade-off between throughput efficiency and multicast redundancy, we evaluate both effective throughput and redundancy under different multicast traffic ratios. Figs. 7(a) and 7(d) show the effective throughput and redundancy for a multicast traffic ratio of 25%, respectively. At low offered traffic rates, e.g., 5 Gb/s, all three schemes exhibit similar effective throughput. This is because their system capacities are sufficient to accommodate the traffic load. Similarly, redundancy remains low across the three schemes at such low traffic rates. As the traffic rate increases, performance differences become apparent. In Benchmark 2, where all ONUs operate at 25 Gb/s, the system capacity is constrained by the ONU with the worst channel conditions. Consequently, effective throughput plateaus at 22.18 Gb/s as the traffic rate reaches 25 Gb/s. In contrast, Benchmark 1 allows ONUs to operate at their maximum peak data rates, significantly increasing system capacity. Although the increase in the ONU group results in additional redundancy for multicast services, the relatively

Fig. 8 Latency versus offered traffic rate in the multicast traffic ratio of (a) 25%, (b) 50%, and (c) 75%.

low multicast traffic ratio mitigates its impact on throughput. As a result, Benchmark 1 achieves 27.38 Gb/s effective throughput after the offered traffic rate exceeds 35 Gb/s, exhibiting a 23.44% improvement over Benchmark 2. However, The TAOG-GBDTA scheme with a lower total group count shows a clear advantage over both benchmarks by optimizing ONU grouping to reduce redundancy while maintaining relatively high ONU data rates. After the offered traffic rate exceeds 40 Gb/s, TAOG achieves over 30 Gb/s effective throughput, outperforming Benchmark 1 and Benchmark 2 by 9.93% and 35.71%, respectively.

Figs. 7(b) and 7(e) present the effective throughput and redundancy for a multicast traffic ratio of 50%, respectively. In terms of Benchmark 2, the effective throughput remains unchanged across all traffic rates, as it does not generate redundancy and is therefore unaffected by the multicast traffic ratio. However, Benchmark 1 experiences a decrease in effective throughput due to the higher multicast traffic ratio. After the offered traffic rate exceeds 20 Gb/s, redundancy in Benchmark 1 nearly doubles compared to the scenario with the multicast traffic ratio of 25%, reaching close to 30 Gb/s. Consequently, effective throughput at 50 Gb/s drops to 19.89 Gb/s, which is 27.36% lower than its performance in the previous scenario. Moreover, Benchmark 1 underperforms compared to Benchmark 2, with its effective throughput being 10.39% lower at 50 Gb/s. In contrast, TAOG-GBDTA maintains a high effective throughput, achieving 24.61 Gb/s at 50 Gb/s, which is 23.73% and 10.91% higher than Benchmarks 1 and 2, respectively. This improvement is attributed to the abilities of the TAOG-GBDTA scheme to strictly limit redundancy and maintain high data rates. The redundancy remains at 12.07 Gb/s under the traffic rate of 50 Gb/s, exhibiting a reduction of 56.72% compared to Benchmark 1.

Figs. 7(c) and 7(f) exhibit the effective throughput and redundancy for a multicast traffic ratio of 75%, respectively. When multicast traffic dominates the offered traffic, the high ONU data rates in Benchmark 1 are negated by the substantial redundancy caused by ONU grouping. As a result, effective throughput decreases further, reaching only 16.75 Gb/s after the traffic rate exceeds 35 Gb/s, which is lower than both TAOG-GBDTA and Benchmark 2. In this high-multicast scenario, the effective throughput of TAOG-GBDTA also declines and approaches that of Benchmark 2 at lower traffic rates (i.e., <25 Gb/s). This is because adopting higher data rates inevitably increases the ONU group number, leading to higher redundancy. Therefore, TAOG tends to group ONUs into fewer groups with lower data rates rather than maintain high data rates. In this case, however, the performance improvement is primarily attributed to the GBDTA algorithm, which plays a critical role in dynamically allocating time slots based on accurate ONU grouping information. Unlike legacy downstream scheduling mechanisms, GBDTA enables more precise bandwidth allocation tailored to the current network conditions, thereby enhancing effective throughput. Despite challenges in finding optimal ONU grouping solutions, TAOG-GBDTA still achieves effective throughput growth at higher traffic rates, reaching 23.73 Gb/s at 50 Gb/s, which exhibits improvements of 41.6% and 6.89% over Benchmarks 1 and 2, respectively. Furthermore, TAOG-GBDTA keeps redundancy consistently low, below 10 Gb/s regardless of the offered traffic rate, whereas the redundancy of Benchmark 1 surges to 45 Gb/s after the offered traffic rate exceeds 35 Gb/s. In summary, in all three multicast traffic scenarios, the proposed TAOG-GBDTA scheme achieves higher effective throughput than the two benchmarks. By optimizing ONU grouping, TAOG-GBDTA effectively reduces redundancy, enabling the Flexible-rate PON system to adapt efficiently to varying network scenarios.

2. Latency

Since effective throughput can significantly affect the packet latency during downstream transmission, we further evaluate the latency performance of three schemes under three scenarios. We begin by analyzing the mean latency. Fig. 8(a) illustrates the packet latency when the multicast traffic ratio is 25%. The curves represent the mean latency, while the shaded regions indicate the range between the maximum (upper bound) and minimum (lower bound) latency. At low offered traffic rates (e.g., below 10 Gb/s), all three schemes exhibit low latency, i.e., less than 200 μ s. Here, in all three schemes, a main component in packet latency is the propagation delay, which averages 75 μ s. The queuing delay in all three schemes is relatively low as the system capacities are sufficient to handle the offered traffic load without congestion. As the traffic rate rises, Benchmark 2 experiences a significant latency increase beyond 20 Gb/s, reaching 34.49 ms at 50 Gb/s, because of the sharp rise in the queuing delay. The performance is consistent

with its limited effective throughput due to operating at the lowest data rate. Benchmark 1 shows lower latency than Benchmark 2, reaching approximately 27.72 ms at 50 Gb/s, owing to its higher system capacity. The TAOG-GBDTA scheme outperforms both benchmarks, exhibiting the lowest latency of 21.5 ms at 50 Gb/s, as it has the highest effective throughput and significantly reduces queuing delays.

Fig. 8(b) shows the latency under a 50% multicast traffic ratio. At 5Gb/s, Benchmark 1 has the lowest latency among the three schemes, but it experiences a sharper latency rise after exceeding 15 Gb/s compared to the previous scenario, as the higher multicast traffic ratio increases the redundancy. At 50 Gb/s, Benchmark 1 reaches a latency of approximately 37.11 ms, which is higher than that of Benchmark 2 (35.70 ms). Compared with the benchmarks, TAOG-GBDTA consistently achieves the lowest latency after the offered traffic rate exceeds 10 Gb/s, maintaining less than 25 ms.

Fig. 8(c) shows the latency under a 75% multicast traffic ratio. In this scenario, Benchmark 1 suffers the highest latency among the three schemes, as its redundancy overwhelms the system, resulting in a latency of 41.87 ms at 50 Gb/s. The performance of Benchmark 2 is similar to the previous scenarios, but its latency is still higher than TAOG-GBDTA. This is because the GBDTA algorithm mitigates the queuing delays caused by low data rates of ONUs, which exhibit a latency of 28.41 ms at 50 Gb/s. This implies that both ONU grouping and bandwidth allocation optimizations in TAOG-GBDTA effectively suppress the increase in latency.

Regarding maximum and minimum latency, all three schemes exhibit a small latency range (i.e., the difference between the maximum and minimum latency). As the traffic rate increases, the latency range generally expands. Among the three schemes, Benchmark 1 exhibits the largest latency range. This is because the latency varies significantly across different ONU groups. At a traffic rate of 50 Gb/s, its latency range reaches 10.57 ms, 3.75 ms, and 2.48 ms in the 25%, 50%, and 75% multicast traffic ratio scenarios, respectively. In contrast, Benchmark 2 has the smallest latency range, with a maximum latency range of no more than 2 ms in all three scenarios, as the uniform ONU data rate leads to a more concentrated latency distribution. The proposed TAOG-GBDTA scheme falls between the two benchmarks, with a latency range of 5.82 ms, 3.75 ms, and 2.45 ms at 50 Gb/s in the 25%, 50%, and 75% multicast traffic ratio scenarios, respectively. This is attributed to the TAOG algorithm, which reduces latency variation compared to Benchmark 1 while maintaining flexibility.

5. CONCLUSION

An enhanced downstream scheduling protocol has been proposed and evaluated to address the challenges of scheduling downstream multicast services while managing the trade-offs between redundancy and system capacity in flexible-rate PONs.

The proposed protocol includes the TAOG algorithm for ONU grouping and the GBDTA algorithm for bandwidth allocation. The TAOG algorithm dynamically adjusts ONU groupings to minimize multicast redundancy while preserving high ONU data rates. Meanwhile, the GBDTA algorithm optimizes downstream time slot allocation to better satisfy service demands in multicast scenarios by considering both redundancy and ONU data rates.

Exhaustive simulation results show that the TAOG-GBDTA scheme significantly enhances effective throughput and reduces redundancy under varying multicast traffic ratios (i.e., 25%, 50%, and 75%). It also achieves lower latency across various traffic scenarios, demonstrating improved scheduling efficiency. Furthermore, TAOG-GBDTA achieves a balance between reducing the total group count and maintaining a high average data rate during the operation, demonstrating its adaptability to dynamic network environments.

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